

CS TRACK
Investigating Citizen Science

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Availability of information on citizen science activities, checked against the Activities & Dimensions Grid of Citizen Science on the basis of some projects

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Executive summary	<p>In Report D1.1 (Framework Conceptual Model) (Strähle, Urban et al., 2021) and Strähle & Urban (2022) the authors of this report systematically analysed how citizen science activities have been conceptualised, categorised and analysed. The detailed outcome of this is the Activities & Dimensions Grid of Citizen Science demonstrating forms citizen science can take and on what dimensions citizen science activities can depend.</p> <p>The research questions were:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Which information on citizen science activities is online available that matches the Activity & Dimension Grid of Citizen Science or goes beyond it? • Is there any contradictory information? • What can be the reason for the availability or non-availability of information about citizen science activities? • How does/could this impact on the CS Track's recommendations? <p>Research on a few projects showed that there was in none of the cases enough and sometimes only a fraction of the information available that can be important to answer the question, which benefit and caveats, barriers and enablers, incentives and disincentives citizen science activities may have (see Activity & Dimensions Grid of Citizen Science). Giving information is a question of transparency, although there can be sensitive issues that need to be kept secret. Standards for transparent public information would be required for research purposes and citizen science policies, but also for those who are interested in participating.</p>

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1 Concept and rationale

This report is an outcome of the Horizon 2020 project CS Track which is funded by the European Commission under the Science with and for Society Work Programme¹. The aim of CS Track is to broaden the knowledge about citizen science and the impact citizen science activities can have. This overall objective is achieved by understanding and characterising citizen science activities so that one can say how they can be improved in terms of maximising their benefit for all participants and stakeholders, citizen and professional scientists, policymakers and funders, while meeting scientific standards of validity and reliability, paying attention to caveats and potential pitfalls, and respecting research integrity and ethics. The CS Track consortium investigates a large and diverse set of citizen science activities, discusses good practices and formulates knowledge-based policy recommendations in order to maximise the potential benefit of citizen science activities on individual citizens, organisations, and society at large.

In Report D1.1 (Framework Conceptual Model) (Strähle, Urban et al., 2021) and Strähle & Urban (2022) the authors of this report systematically analysed how citizen science activities have been conceptualised and categorised. The detailed result of this is the Activities & Dimensions Grid of Citizen Science demonstrating forms citizen science can take and on what dimensions citizen science activities can depend. The dimensions include the location of participation, requirements for participation, scale, characteristics of the country, respectively countries, the activities take place, the geographic coverage, beings/objects dealt with, funding, initiators and organisers, whom citizen scientists are known to, who participates in the activities, topic areas, scientific disciplines assigned to the activities by the project team and third parties, competences in the team, and promised incentives and remunerations. In the framework of CS Track the consortium uses the explanation of citizen science the European Commission gives in the Science with and for Society Work Programme 2018-2020 (European Commission, 2018):

(...) citizen science should be understood broadly, covering a range of different levels of participation, from raising public knowledge of science, encouraging citizens to participate in the scientific process by observing, gathering and processing data, right up to setting scientific agenda and co-designing and implementing science-related policies. It could also involve publication of results and teaching science. (p. 41)

This is also the explanation of citizen science the Activities & Dimensions Grid of Citizen Science is based on. The activities have been categorised into four areas: Input for research policy, taking part in research projects, development and innovation, and school projects.

The Grid can be used for a clearer differentiation between a variety of activities that are called citizen science and their possible characteristics. Such differentiations are necessary before one can attempt to identify possible pitfalls, ethical aspects as well

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as aspects of inclusion and exclusion, provided that sufficient information is available about these activities.

The research questions were:

- Which information on citizen science activities is online available that matches the Activity & Dimension Grid of Citizen Science or goes beyond it?
- Is there any contradictory information?
- What can be the reason for the availability or non-availability of information about citizen science activities?
- How does/could this impact on the CS Track's recommendations?

2 Methodology

Selection of projects

The goal was to get a broad diversity of CS (related) activities from the database that was created in WP2 in order to try out the AD Grid and recommendations how to use the results discussed in CS Track.

First, a keyword-based database research carried out by Miriam Calvera Isabal resulted in 3318 projects in German or English language. WLW took a simple – but not perfect - random selection from the list based on the project description in the database, cutting off the first 40 characters including signs, numbers and blanks and sort the reminders of the text fields alphabetically. The number 41 had been the last number of the public lottery “6 aus 45” from Sunday, 16/10/2022².

Projects that had no text in the description field were sorted alphabetically after cutting off the first 4 letters. This provided a list of projects in different order and the first of this list became objects of the investigation. The projects were further selected using following criteria:

Projects were excluded if they have not been established in an EU Member State or in a country associated to the Horizon 2020 Framework Programme for Research and Innovation.

On order to get a diversity of projects into the sample, it was decided to limit the number of projects from one source: no more than 2 projects with and 2 projects without a description field should come from one platform. Otherwise, we would have analysed mostly international projects from Zooniverse, iNaturalist or SciStarter. Another criterion was that the project is/was located in a country participating in Horizon 2020 as an EU Member State or as an Associated Country, i.e. including Switzerland and the United Kingdom.

About 85 projects showed no content in the database field “description”. After checking only the first 40 of these, it was confirmed that in most of these cases there was really no online information on them, so the rest was skipped. The next projects selected provided a description field with content.

The project organisers were contacted. In a first mail they were asked, if they found that their project contained CS activities and secondly, if there was further publicly available information on their projects. In addition, the web was searched for more information about these projects-

We ended up with a selection of the following projects, which we began to investigate:

1. Wissenschaftscafé Bern
2. Wissenschaftstage Sport 2006
3. Digitalisierung/Erschließung von Objekten: Erschließung der Bryozoensammlung von Professor Voigt (1905-2004) im Senckenberg

² See <https://www.gewinnabfrage.at/lotto/lottozahlen/16-10-2022>.

Forschungsinstitut, Frankfurt am Main (*Digitalisation/Cataloguing of objects: Cataloguing of Professor Voigt's collection of bryozoans*)

4. RainGauge, resp. CrowdWater
5. Forschende Senior:innen (*Senior citizens doing research*)
6. Snapshot Gondwana
7. Projekt Plumage

Skipped were the following projects with the reason(s) for not taking them into the sample indicated under "criteria for inclusion/exclusion".

Random sequence of projects	Name of the project	Criteria for inclusion/exclusion
1	Wissenschaftscafé Bern	Preselected but not citizen science
2	Wissenschaftstage Sport 2006	Preselected but not citizen science
3	Bangalow Koalas	Australian project
4	Erschließung der Bryozoensammlung von Professor Voigt (1905-2004) im Senckenberg Forschungsinstitut	Included
5	White Leeds Arid Wetlands	Australian project
6	NHMA Batumi	No description
7	Test BioActivity Javier	No description
8	Baku Botanical Garden	Project in Azerbaijan & no description
9	Bern forensische Tiere	No description
10	Wild fungi of Poland	No description
11	Mein Garten	No description
12	Baku Old City test	Project in Azerbaijan & no description
13	Dach Pumpwerk Meilen	No description
14	Rios Saludables de Osa - Costa Rica	Project in Costa Rica & no description
15	TEST_asam	No description
16	UÖ18_Aufgabe-5_caregus	No description
17	DFV2019_Lok17_RøsnæsVRøsnæsgården	No description
18	Fauna & Flora of Neidling 15 (LoVer Austria)	No description
19	Flora Íslands	No description

20	Fauna Islands	No description
21	Fauna Survey	No description
22	Stream Explorers	Project in the USA & no description
23	Stream Flow Monitoring in Upstate New York	Project in the USA & no description
24	Terrapin Tally Application	Project in the USA & no description
25	Essbare Wildpflanzen CH	No description
26	NT Fauna Surveys (Citizen Science)	No description
27	Frühblüher CH	No description
28	fvesca_trial	No description
29	citsci.org	Project in the USA & no description
30	A backyard in Arezzo	No description
31	Incident Reporting System	Project in the USA& no description
32	CrowdWater Raingauge	Included
33	Snake Fungal Disease of the Carolinas Project	Project in the USA& no description
34	Downeast Maine Shellfish Sustainability Project	Project in the USA & no description
35	Dreiecksland	No description
36	Project #35	No description
37	Winter birds monitoring Korea	Project in Korea & no description
38	Grüner Fleck	No description
39	Butterflies and other pollinators of the Crested Butte Wildflower Festival	Project in Australia & no description
40	Butterflies of Geelong Region	Project in Australia & no description
41	Butterfly and Pollinator Observations at the Crested Butte Wildflower Festival	No description
42	FlowerGarden	No description
43	HORNERO - Citizen Science	No description
44	INVAFISH	No description
45	Wildflowers of Romania	No description
46	Übung-6-UI18-kruscnad	No description
47	Public spaces and health	No description
48	Nannie's parents' driveway	No description

49	Biodiversity Hong Kong	No description
50	The Kestrel Project	No description
51	Wheel Cactus Mapping and Biological Control in Victoria	No description
52	Problemas de Manejo CEN - Observaciones de Campo	No description
53	edibles	No description
54	Scarlets and Blues	No description
55	De olho na costa	No description
56	Trillium Sessile Project	No description
57	Golan	No description
58	Urban bio-cultural diversity	No description
59	Urban Plants CH	No description
60	Flying Fox Monitoring Project	No description
61	ASIANOPlast	No description
62	Pflanzen in und um Augsburg	No description
63	Tucson Green Infrastructure Rapid Assessment	No description
64	Solsones Biodiversity	No description
65	WQ-Monitoring	No description
66	Microplastics at Otter Point Creek	No description
67	Onopordum thistle biocontrol	No description
68	DJN Ortsgruppe Göttingen	No description
69	Orno-Ostryon	No description
70	Monitoring Nesting Behaviour - Coastal Raptor Nests in Redland City	No description
71	European Raptor	No description
72	NSW Post-fire Reptiles Monitoring Project	No description
73	Sunspotter	No description
74	Colorado Herptile Information by the Public System	No description
75	Colorado Herptile Public Information System	No description
76	Monarch Butterflies	No description

77	Distribution of Bornean Herpetofauna	No description
78	Environmental Justice in Baltimore	No description
79	Makers Local 256	No description
80	Superwasp: Black hole hunters	No description
81	(Non-Sevengill) Sharks of California	No description
82	Invasive Species Mapping	No description
83	Mount Evelyn Fauna and Flora	No description
84	DLR Test Project	No description
85	Monitoring <i>Kordyana brasiliensis</i> on Wandering Trad	No description
86	Monitoring Nesting Behaviour - Coastal Raptor Nests in Redland City	No description
87	UÖ1_Übung-5_zwingjon	No description
88	Halbury Parklands	No description
89	Zoo Vienna	No description
90	Citizen Science Monitoring for Long Island Eastern Box Turtles	No description
91	Sapphire Coast Marine Society Surveys	Project in the USA
92	Forschende Senioren/innen	Included
93	Snapshot Gondwana	Included
94	Project Plumage	incuded

3 Results

Wissenschaftscafé Bern

Identified as main source: Science et Cité, <https://www.science-et-cite.ch/de/wissenschaftscafe-bern-2>

Country	Switzerland
Geographic reach	Regional
Feedback from project organisers	Organisers do not consider it as citizen science.
Status	Ongoing
Science communication	A series of science café events since 2010. Website indicates organisers, public and private sponsors.
Area	n/a
Activity	n/a

Information on website is on a science communication event.

Wissenschaftstage Sport 2006

Identified as main source: Science et Cité, <https://www.science-et-cite.ch/de/wissenschaftstage-sport>

Country	Switzerland
Geographic reach	Regional
Feedback from project organisers	Organisers do not consider it citizen science.
Status	Finished
Area	n/a
Activity	n/a

The project consisted of a series of science related events on sports, classic science communication activities. The audience could learn about research projects, make fitness tests, discuss with experts, and watch sports related movies. The website indicates organisers and academic cooperation partners.

Digitalisierung/Erschließung von Objekten: Erschließung der Bryozoensammlung von Professor Voigt (1905-2004) im Senckenberg Forschungsinstitut, Frankfurt am Main (*Digitalisation/Cataloguing of objects: Cataloguing of Professor Voigt's collection of bryozoans*)

Identified as main source: DFG project database,
<https://gepris.dfg.de/gepris/projekt/203068139?context=projekt&task=showDetail&id=203068139&>

Country	Germany
Geographic reach	Local
Using the term "citizen science"	No
Status	Finished
Area	2 / Participating in research
Activity	Knowledge management
Location of participation	Physical place: Separate institution
Requirements for participation	Not indicated
Scale	Not indicated
Characteristics of country	Germany is a democracy with high life expectancy
Geographic coverage	Local
Beings and/or objects dealt with	Not clearly indicated what citizens do or what they handle with, however, no living beings are involved. As it is not specified, it is possible that citizen scientists deal with damageable, rare or valuable objects.
Funding	Government (non-military)
Initiators of citizen science	Researchers in the field or research organisations, palaeontologist
Organisers	Publicly funded organization, Research institution
Citizen scientists are known to	Not indicated. However, since the activity took place at the premises of the research institute, they are at least known to the organisers. It is not visible if the participants know each other as well, if they were invited to share activities.
Partners cooperating as citizen scientists	Not indicated
Individuals as citizen scientist(s)	Not indicated
Individuals as "traditional scientists"	Professional researchers/scientists, palaeontologist
Topic areas and/or disciplines	Palaeontology
Disciplinary competences in project organisation teams:	Palaeontology

Incentives and remunerations promised	Not indicated
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The funded activities consisted in registering of a collection of more than 300.000 fossils in a database. The project was funded by DFG (Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft) for the period of 2012-2016. More information about this collection is available at <https://www.senckenberg.de/de/institute/senckenberg-gesellschaft-fuer-naturforschung-frankfurt-main/abt-marine-zoologie/marine-evertebraten-3/marine-evertebraten-iii-sammlung/>.

Other sources: A Web search did not result in any more information on the roles or tasks of "citizen scientists". On its website the research institute offers opportunities to participate in research projects as a citizen scientist: <https://gemeinsamforschen.senckenberg.de/>.

Rain Gauge, respectively CrowdWater

Identified as main source: project website: <https://crowdwater.ch/de/start-2/>

Country	Switzerland
Geographic reach	Global
Using the term "citizen science"	Yes
Status	Ongoing
Area	2 / Participating in research
Activity	Data collection
Location of participation	Physical place: Outside in unspecified environments
Requirements for participation	Material: Smartphones, Non-Material: Specific training offered might be a requirement
Scale	Not indicated
Characteristics of country	Switzerland is a democracy with high life expectancy
Geographic coverage	Global
Beings and/or objects dealt with	Objects/non-sentient beings: None
Funding	Yes, by Swiss National Science Fund. Link to entry in the fund's database provided.
Initiators of citizen science	Researchers in the field or research organisations: Hydrologists
Organisers	Publicly funded organization: University
Citizen scientists are known to	Not indicated
Partners cooperating as citizen scientists	Individual citizens

Individuals as citizen scientist(s)	Not indicated
Individuals as "traditional scientists"	Professional researchers/scientists: Hydrologists, geographers
Topic areas and/or disciplines	Hydrology
Disciplinary competences in project organisation teams:	Hydrology, geography
Incentives and remunerations promised	Symbolic incentives

The website presents the project objectives, the organisers and their team (including former team members), actual hydrological research by team members, explains in a language easy to understand what the organisers consider as citizen science, opportunities and requirements for participating as a citizen scientist, and the CrowdWater app citizen scientists are expected to use. Information on privacy and data protection policies and measures is provided by offering a link to the app developer's terms of use. By starting monthly championships among citizen scientists, the project makes use of gamification. Scientific papers – peer reviewed ones and preprints – are listed with their DOI and explained in a language easy to understand. Collected data – from Europe, Africa, the Americas, Asia and Australia - are available for download and presented on a geographic map that allows to download data for regions one is interested in. The project team publishes a regular newsletter in German and in English, an interested public can subscribe to. Newspaper articles about the project show media coverage about the project. The project is also present on Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, YouTube and LinkedIn. Teachers can download teaching materials from the project website. A dashboard allows for retrieving actual statistical data on monthly active users of the app, on what kind of data have been collected and where and in what period.

Other sources: The project is listed on SciStarter.com, Anecdata.org³ and *Österreich forscht*⁴ Additionally, several scientific papers were published on crowdwater.ch.

Forschende Senior:innen (Senior citizens doing research)

Identified as main source: *Schweiz forscht*,
<https://www.schweizforscht.ch/projekte/projektarchiv/forschende-senioren-innen>

Country	Switzerland
Geographic reach	Regional
Using the term "citizen science"	Citizen scientists are referred to as <i>Laienforscher:innen</i> (lay researchers).
Status	Finished

³ <https://www.anecdata.org/projects/view/733>

⁴ <https://www.citizen-science.at/projekte/crowdwater>

Area	2/ Participating in research
Activities	Determining research questions, data collection, data preparation & processing, action research
Area	3/ Development & innovation
Activity	Technical development
Location of participation	Physical place: At home, probably other people's home and university department
Requirements for participation	Material: Not specified; Non-material: Specific training offered might be a requirement
Scale	Not indicated
Characteristics of country	Switzerland is a democracy with high life expectancy
Geographic coverage	National
Beings and/or objects dealt with	Sentient beings: Humans
Funding	Not indicated
Initiators of citizen science	Researchers in the field or research organisations
Organisers	Publicly funded organisations: University of Applied Sciences
Citizen scientists are known to	Organisers
Partners cooperating as citizen scientists	Individual citizens
Individuals as citizen scientist(s)	Lay persons in the field
Individuals as "traditional scientists"	Professional researchers/scientists
Topic areas and/or disciplines	Social sciences, technical engineering
Disciplinary competences in project organisation teams	Sociology indicated
Incentives and remunerations promised	None indicated

The project is presented on the website *Schweiz forscht*, which, similar to SciStarter and platforms like *Österreich forscht* and *Bürger schaffen Wissen*, presents opportunities for participating in real research as a citizen scientist. Similar to action research, the presentation stresses the importance of citizen participation in research and development and frames the project as participatory research. The organisers target senior citizens, who are invited to join a Living Lab to test technical assistance systems at home. The organisers call citizen scientists lay researchers and offer to actively involve them in the whole R&D process from topic identification through to the implementation and evaluation of the project. Regular meetings between organisers and lay researchers are mentioned, so it can be fairly assumed that professional and lay researchers involved know each other. According to the information provided, the lay researchers are trained in applying research methods required for contributing to the project. To evaluate the lay researchers' view of the research approach, they are asked to fill in an evaluation questionnaire developed

by the project owners. The website of the project owners does not list a project called *Forschende Senior:innen* but reveals that Living Labs on Ambient Assisted Living Systems and similar technical systems are a R&D focus of the institute. The project database of the institute lists several of such R&D projects with business partners developing such technologies.

The project organisers published a paper on their participatory approach in a newsletter of *Stiftung Mitarbeit*, a philanthropic foundation dedicated to civic engagement and citizen participation. This paper provides additional information about the project without contradicting the information available at *Schweiz forscht*. According to this paper (Lehmann et al., 2017), the project positions itself as participatory research ("partizipative Forschung") or action research. Senior citizens formed a research group that, closely supported and guided by academic staff, decided on research topics and research questions. Subsequently they were trained in conducting qualitative structured interviews and developed interview guidelines together with academic staff before going into the field. Members of the research group conducted interviews and analysed them. In the paper mentioned above the project organisers reflect on their experiences with these participatory research processes and present lessons learnt and what the research groups says about them. The project was evaluated.

Other sources: A paper on the project was sent by the organisers, but no additional sources were found.

Snapshot Gondwana

Identified as main source: Zooniverse.org,
<https://www.zooniverse.org/projects/meredithspalmer/snapshot-gondwana>

Country	South Africa
Geographic reach	Global
Using the term "citizen science"	No
Status	Finished
Area	2 / Participating in research
Activity	Data collection
Location of participation	ICT environment: Online platforms;
Requirements for participation	Material: Not specified, but internet access is necessary. Non-material: Online tutorial (not clear if obligatory)
Scale	Not indicated
Characteristics of country	n/a because online
Geographic coverage	Global
Beings and/or objects dealt with	Objects: Undamageable (photos)

Funding	Not indicated; some funding by a company or foundation on whose estate the camera traps have been set up cannot be excluded.
Initiators of citizen science	Not indicated
Organisers	Three rangers
Citizen scientists are known to	Not indicated
Partners cooperating as citizen scientists	Not indicated
Individuals as citizen scientist(s)	Not indicated
Individuals as "traditional scientists"	One graduate listed
Topic areas and/or disciplines	Zoology
Disciplinary competences in project organisation teams	Zoology
Incentives and remunerations promised	None indicated

According to the information provided on Zooniverse, the project team asked citizen scientists to identify animals on photos shot by camera traps in a conservation area in South Africa. The task was performed online. On the website a team of three project owners is presented. At least one of them has completed tertiary education in zoology; all of them work for the game reserve in which the photos have been taken. As stated, the overall objective of the project was to enhance the reserve management plan. A short tutorial in plain language provided a quick training of citizen scientists. The project website does not present outcomes of the project.

Project Plumage

Identified as main source: Zooniverse.org,
<https://www.zooniverse.org/projects/ghthomas/project-plumage>

Country	United Kingdom
Geographic reach	Global
Use of the term "citizen science"	No
Status	Finished
Area	2 / Participating in research
Activity	Data collection; data preparation & processing
Location of participation	ICT environment: Online platforms
Requirements for participation	Material: not specified, but internet access is necessary. Non-material: online tutorial (not clear if obligatory)
Scale	Not indicated
Characteristics of country	n/a because online

Geographic coverage	Global
Beings and/or objects dealt with	Objects: undamageable (photos)
Funding	Government (non-military)
Initiators of citizen science	Researchers in the field or research organisations
Organisers	Researchers in the field or research organisations
Citizen scientists are known to	Not indicated
Partners cooperating as citizen scientists	Not indicated
Individuals as citizen scientist(s)	Not indicated
Individuals as "traditional scientists"	Professional researchers/scientists
Topic areas and/or disciplines	Ornithology
Disciplinary competences in project organisation teams	2 evolutionary biologists, 1 zoologist, 1 museologist
Incentives and remunerations promised	None indicated

Citizen scientists are asked to identify key areas of bird plumages and their colouration by marking these areas on photos. The website explains the project objectives, the tasks to be performed, how to perform them, and what is done with the data citizen scientists collect. Additional information is available at the museum's website. The guiding research interest is to both measure and better understand how colour diversity of plumage has come to be.⁵ The project team consists of professional scientists, three of them biologists, one of them a museologist. The photos are provided by a museum, the research coordinator is a professional scientist at a university. The research is funded by the European Research Council, however, neither the project title nor the grant agreement number is indicated. A short tutorial in plain language provided a quick training of citizen scientists. On the website presents some plumage collections citizen scientists worked on and citizen scientists' favourite plumages.

Other sources: Both <https://www.nhm.ac.uk/take-part/citizen-science/project-plumage.html> and <https://eu-citizen.science/project/47> refer to the Zooniverse website as the main project website.

⁵ <https://www.nhm.ac.uk/take-part/citizen-science/project-plumage.html>

4 Discussion

Research on the above-mentioned projects showed that for none of them publicly available information on them is not sufficient to fully assess what benefits and caveats, barriers and enablers, incentives and disincentives their citizen science activities may have. In some cases, this information was only partly useful to answer this. This is consistent with earlier findings (Strähle, Urban et al., 2021; Calvera-Isabal et al., 2023).

Several projects used platforms such as *Zooniverse*, *SciStarter* and national citizen science platforms such as *Schweiz forscht*, *Österreich forscht* and *Bürger schaffen Wissen* as the main medium to display online information about their CS activities and had no website of their own or other forms to give more details. These platforms have different densities of information. as they are based on different design concepts, can have different goals and meet different needs. For example, *Zooniverse* displays complete projects, with information about the project goals, the people behind a project, FAQ sections, explanations of the tasks, documentation of the results of other citizen scientists and more. The presentation of the projects is more or less standardised due to the predominantly uniform navigation bar. The tabs "About", "Classify", "Talk" and "Collect" appeared in all the projects examined. Through this structure, it is practically already predetermined that projects based on *Zooniverse* must be crowdsourcing projects. *SciStarter*, on the other hand, functions as an advertising platform for project operators who are looking for citizen scientists. The information that can be found about a project on this platform is scarce, information that could be found about the selected projects on this platform is scarce, but there is the possibility to link to a project website that is not part of *SciStarter*. It would be worth a separate investigation to find out how often project organisers make use of this option, in the case of the projects studied this did not happen regularly. *iNaturalist* is mainly a platform for documenting the results of Citizen Science activities, such as photographs of plants and animals. The focus here is not on recruiting Citizen scientists, but on a specific form of crowdsourcing: making photographs of plant and animal species available. *Zooniverse* projects work with photos and videos analysed by citizen scientists, while projects on *iNaturalist* provide such visual material. The platform allows information to be published about the projects in the context of which these documentations are produced, and it is also possible to link to project websites. As far as insight could be gained during the research, this is not used very often; the information about the projects was sparse. Platforms such as *Schweiz forscht* also serve to recruit citizen scientists. The information texts can be designed relatively freely. Provided the texts are not subject to character restrictions, this allows for more extensive information and, of course, links to further information outside the website.

Such platforms carry a potential to pave the way towards a culture of providing more making information public in a more structured way than is often the case at present. Standards are needed for what information about citizen science activities should be provided and in what form.

Information given on websites and other online resources varies. No project gave extensive information on all areas, activities and dimensions that should be specified according to the GRID. Often the information is vague. Two of the projects – the Swiss

ones - we contacted responded to our information requests. For projects listed on Zooniverse no contact information was indicated. Therefore, the project leaders could not be contacted directly.

There could be solid reasons not to give information on one or several aspects of a project. Examples are sensitive data and privacy protection. Also, activities could take place in sensitive environments like biotopes of endangered species or archaeological sites, which should be kept secret to protect them.

Nevertheless, if the information given is relatively thin, in-depth research is quite difficult if not impossible.

Areas & Activities

Two projects fell into none of the areas of the Grid but also were not considered as citizen science activities by the respective organisers. None of the projects seems to contain activities that fall into Area 1, decision making on research agendas, or Area 4, school projects with minors. Most of the citizen science activities indicated by the projects fell into Area 2, participation in research. One project was entirely dedicated to Area 3 activities, development and Innovation.⁶

Location of participation

Relatively clearly indicated in all projects. Two projects took place online (Project Plumage, Snapshot Gondwana), one outdoors (CrowdWater), one probably at the premises of a research institute (Collection Voigt), and one probably mostly at the homes of the "citizen scientists" (seniors). Privacy protection needs most attention in the last case, it can also be an issue in online activities.

Requirements

This dimension is to determine if there are conditions for participation or if everybody can participate. For activities that took place only online, it is clear that internet access via a computer or smartphone is required. For participating in four of the projects (CrowdWater, Forschende Senior:innen, Snapshot Gondwana, Project Plumage), participants received training of different scope. It is not quite clear how far these trainings are obligatory conditions for participation or just a service to inform participants. Three of the projects offered online tutorials, one project (Forschende Senior:innen) indicated that they trained citizen scientists in qualitative social research which leaves a lot of room for interpretation of the intensity of this training. In the case of one project there is no indication, if there are any requirements to become a voluntary for which activities.

⁶ See Strähle, Urban et al. (2021), chapter 7.2.

Scale of the citizen science activities

The Grid distinguishes between two sub-dimensions of scale: the number of participants and the amount of unpaid work, which is specified by its intensity and its duration.

Both is well documented in Project Plumage that indicates that work takes two minutes per bird, which would allow for try-outs to verify. Multiplied by number of classified birds one comes to an amount of work measured in hours spent by volunteers.

In the case of online activities and anonymous participation it could be difficult or impossible to know how many “citizen scientists” are involved. There may be other reasons not to indicate scale. For one thing, it may change over time. Additionally, at the beginning of a project, there may be only few participants, and organisers may not want to make this public as it might not encourage others to join.

Characteristics of country

The selection criteria impact on the characteristics of countries. The languages were restricted to English and German and only countries were involved that were eligible for Horizon 2020 projects. There were international projects, but none of them were specifically addressing locations outside democracies.

Beings and objects dealt with

In the two merely online projects participants do not handle any originals but only digital copies. These copies are undamageable by “citizen scientists”, of course. In the case of the project on Palaeolithic bryozoans it is possible that people handle valuable objects of the collection, but it is not explained what the exact activities are and how they are carried out.

The senior citizens are in a kind of hybrid role: they participate as “citizen scientists” but they are also objects/subjects of research. They are identifiable by the organisers and they meet with other participants as well and can be identified by them. Hence, they deal with sentient beings, namely humans, which always raises a bundle of ethical questions. Some more information how or how far the seniors’ privacy can be protected would be helpful. Even more importantly, in the case that very personal and intimate issues are debated, psychological damage cannot be ruled out. There should be some information which topics are to be addressed or more specifically not addressed, and some specification what is offered as mental safeguards.

Funding, Initiators and Organisers

Funding, initiators and organisers are three separated dimensions which can be described as who is behind a citizen science activity: For instance, it could be an academic institution, an environmental civil society organisation, a private enterprise or a group of citizens themselves, a different entity or any combination of them. Who gives the money for a certain citizen science activity contains a bundle of information that is highly important to participants as well to evaluators. It indicates possible conflicts of interests and can also show some ideological or political orientation or who could take influence on the activity.

Funding

For three projects, sources of funding were indicated (Cataloguing of Professor Voigt's collection of bryozoans, CrowdWater, Project Plumage). All three of them received public funds. The funding of the two other projects were not as clearly indicated on the main source. Additionally, the pictures for Snapshot Safari are taken by rangers in a protected environment, but it is not indicated whose property it is. Theoretically – although not exactly probable – owners could take economic advantage of the project. Thus, all information on funding should be given including all in-kind contributions such as property and means that are given or lent to citizen scientists.

Initiators

In the investigated projects, the initiators seem to be the same as those who organise(d) the citizen science activity.

Organisers

Four projects were organised by scientists from research organisations, Snapshot Gondwana had different organisers.

“Citizen scientists” are known to

In an online project like Project Plumage or Snapshot Gondwana participants are probably anonymous. The same may be true for CrowdWater. And, of course, when “citizen scientists” catalogue fossils at the premises of an institute, they are known to the organisers of this activity, too. The senior citizens (“action research”) are necessarily known to the organisers and probably to each other, too. Touched by several dimensions, privacy is a more technical issue in online projects and a most sensitive issue in “action research”. The degree of sensitivity depends how much personal information is given by the participants. Safeguarding privacy is a challenge and opens up different ethical questions.

Partners cooperating as „citizen scientists”

All investigated projects invited individuals directly to participate. None of them indicated that they cooperate with a school, a hospital, a civil society organisation or any other organisation as a group of “citizen scientists”.

Individuals as „citizen scientists”

“Users” in one project, Lay persons in the field. One project was addressed to a specific age group, although it was not clearly specified, at what minimum age one qualifies as a “senior”, but in this case it might actually be wise not to specify or to exclude anybody who feels that s/he belongs to this group,

Individuals as “traditional scientists”

All projects described the background of their teams. Four of the analysed projects were, respectively are, led by academic scientists. In the fifth project (Snapshot Gondwana) one of the project team members has graduated in zoology.

Topic areas and/or disciplines (Web of Science Research Areas)

As far as they are indicated, the research areas and scientific areas represented in the project teams are ornithology, palaeontology, physical geography, sociology, and zoology.

Incentives and remunerations promised

None of the five investigated projects explicitly promises incentives or a remuneration for “citizen scientists”. Any incentives appear to be symbolic. CrowdWater uses a gamification approach that puts participants in a competition; Project Plumage offered “citizen scientists” to present their favourite plumage photographs.

5 Conclusions

The analysis of the selected projects shows that “citizen science” can refer to substantially different activities. Organisers of two of the selected projects did not consider them as citizen science. The remaining five hardly be compared to each other in terms of potential benefits or caveats, enablers or barriers, incentives or disincentives.

More information about citizen science activities, is a desideratum not only for researchers doing research on citizen science, but also for potential participants in citizen science, policy makers and citizens interested in research policies. Some general information was given on most characteristics of the Grid by most projects, but it was not very detailed. Not only projects with short citizen science activities, but also projects with more complicated tasks should unveil some details about what can be done, where and why. Enough information to judge the scientific soundness of the methods, potential risks for participants and how the information will be used should be given, there is an indication of trainings, but its content is described only vaguely. With the exception of Project Plumage, none of the analysed projects provided even some indication of the workload and possible costs for the citizen scientists. It could be concluded from the description that a smartphone or computer was necessary, but it was not specified how sophisticated or modern these would have to be or how strong the internet connection should be or if older equipment would suffice for participating in a comfortable way.

This does not actually mean that giving all information is a must and there cannot be sound reasons to withhold certain information. For example, when it comes to sensitive issues, which require some secrecy, transparency has limits. Most probably detailed information is often missing or difficult to find, because there has been little development of good practices what information should be made public. Nevertheless, standards for transparency should be discussed and maybe codes of conduct developed: what information should be made public by organisers of citizen science in all cases (e.g., funding, conditions for participation, requirements, etc.) and which information could be kept secret if reasons are made public (e. g., data protection, location of sensitive environments, etc.). In some cases, there may be scientific reasons not to give all details at the beginning in order to prevent influencing those who conduct experiments or report on certain experiences. We do not know if the project owners considered providing some more information and decided against it or if they did not think about it.

One could demand that Citizen Science is more open to the public and gives more public information than traditional science does, for several reasons. One argument for citizen science that is often brought forward by proponents is that citizen science opens up science to the public, hence openness should be a core characteristic. It claims to serve public good. It needs not only to prove its scientific soundness but also the additional benefits, which are often asserted.

Due to a lack of information, the question of what can be reasons for the availability or non-availability of information about citizen science activities allows a more or less speculative answer only,

CS Track also had the task of making policy recommendations on citizen science. Therefore, one of the research questions was how the results of this study could impact on these policy recommendations. The outcomes of this research imply that a broad concept that is not generally understood and is applied to a variety of quite different activities with no discernible common denominator makes it impossible to make recommendations for all these activities that go beyond a very general level. Specific policy recommendations require that sufficient information about the activities and their characteristics according to several dimensions be provided. Because of differences in the dimensions, for example because of the places where these activities take place or because of the required knowledge and skills of the citizen scientists, two activities that look very similar may turn out to be quite different when one looks closer. However, in the case of the projects studied, this information was not available to the desired extent, even though in individual cases quite a lot of information was available on certain aspects of the activities. It can be assumed that these are not exceptional cases, but the rule. This has an impact on the making of policy recommendations in that without detailed research into a wide range of activities, only very general recommendations can be made and not on very safe grounds. This even applies to apparently straight forward, simple activities such as crowdsourcing, which only seem relatively homogeneous.

6 References

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